

OUTLINE

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1. Introduction and overview

The VICO dataset contains geographical, industry and accounting information on 17,854 companies founded starting from 1/1/1988, which have received at least one venture capital or angel investment starting from 1/1/1998 up to 31/12/2014, operating in 7 European countries (Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom) and Israel. Moreover, it provides basic information on 6,839 distinct investors (e.g. investor type, investor experience, and its geographical location), of which 5,172 venture capital (VC) investors and 1,551 business angels (BAs) (plus a small percentage of other investors, e.g. crowdfunding, private equity...). Companies and investors have been involved in 28,023 investment deals, for a total of 52,629 observations (as one or more investors can be involved in each single investment round). VICO also provides information on these investment deals (e.g. deal date, total amount invested). Its uniqueness lies in the overall number of companies, the country coverage, and the extent of information gathered, thanks to the combination of multiple secondary data sources, namely Thompson One Private Equity, Zephyr, Crunchbase and Orbis.

Services currently offered by the VICO infrastructure allows to address a wide range of research questions concerning the characteristics, the evolution and the role of VC in Europe. It has been widely used by a large academic community to study the peculiarities of the European VC market and the effectiveness of different forms of VC in supporting the performance of European start-ups. Results from academic research based on VICO also attracted the attention of policy makers interested in assessing the impact of policy measures aimed at facilitating access to start-ups' finance.

The dataset is operated and maintained by Politecnico di Milano, Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering, located in Via Lambruschini 4/b, Milano, 20156, Italy. It is currently available in the .dta format (Stata)

- ▶ Link to metadata in RCF: <https://rcf.risis2.eu/dataset/12/metadata>
- ▶ Link to documentation in Zenodo: Tenca, Francesca. (2019, July 16). Documentation of RISIS datasets: VICO (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3337991>
- ▶ Link to tutorial in Zenodo: Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering. (2019, August 2). RISIS DATASETS TUTORIALS: VICO (Version 1). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3359000>

2. Activities and Developments in the first reporting period

2.1. Maintenance

The planned VICO maintenance activities for the first year of the project are summarized in the following table 1.

Table 1. Timetable Maintenance M1-M24

Time	Activity
M6	Finalization of the strategy and workplan for VICO maintenance.
M7	Integration of updated information on exits (IPO/M&A) for existing firms in VICO.
M9	Download of venture capital deals and accounting data from source databases (Thomson Reuters Eikon, Zephyr, Crunchbase and Orbis) for the period 2015-2018.
M10	Download of information on exits (IPO/M&A) for new firms.
M11-M23	Integration, geocoding and data cleaning.
M24	First release of updated VICO – MS32 (WP5).

As reported in the table, the main planned activities until M18 included: the download of new data on VC investments and accounting for the period 2015-2018, the integration of information on exits (i.e., IPO and M&A deals), geocoding and data cleaning activities. The latter are planned to be completed by M24. We do not see major deviations from the former workplan. In particular:

1. We completed the integration of information on exit: for all 17,854 firms included in the previous version of VICO, data on IPO and M&A deals, and failures were incorporated into the dataset;
2. For all the 17,854 companies included in the previous version of VICO, accounting data for years 2015-2018 were incorporated into the dataset;
3. We completed the download and integration of all new data from the source databases (Thomson Reuters Eikon, Zephyr, Crunchbase and Orbis) concerning VC deals, VC-backed firms and VC investors. This download was then followed by a process of names disambiguation (through Fuzzy Matching logic and manual checking) for both VC-backed firms and VC investors. This activity lead to the inclusion of more than 16,000 new VC-backed firms and about 7,200 new VC investors. We are now in the process of data cleaning, checking data harmonization and consistency and classification of VC investor types combining information coming from the source databases with manual checks.

The only delay concerns the integration of information on exits for new firms, added to dataset for the years 2015-2018. Nevertheless, since we have already developed a straightforward procedure for the integration of exit data for existing firms, we are confident to complete this activity as planned by M24 for the first release of VICO.

2.2. Deepening

The planned VICO deepening activities for the first year of the project are summarized in the following table 2.

Table 2. Timetable Deepening M1-M24

Time	Activity
M12	Finalization of the strategy and workplan for VICO deepening.
M12-M16	Business model classification of current VICO companies (pilot project).
M12-M18	Classification of investor types (CVC, Business Angels and Crowdfunding).
M18	VICO investors data available for access – MS26 (WP9).
M16-M30	Business model classification of old and newly added VICO companies.
M24	First release of updated VICO – MS32 (WP5).

As reported in the table, the main planned activities until M18 included: finalizing the strategy for VICO deepening, performing the pilot project for business model classification of current VICO companies, and the classification of investors types. We do not see major deviations from the former workplan.

In particular:

1. We completed the pilot project related to the business model classification of current VICO companies. For this pilot, we focused on a particular type of innovative business model that has emerged in the last years: platform-based businesses (e.g. Airbnb). In order to automatically classify companies, we explored a number of alternative strategies that combined information retrieval, data mining and machine learning techniques (e.g. classifiers starting from the description of the business). We followed the next steps:
 - a. We identified the most reliable source of information for the classification, performing 3 different pilots tests. The evaluation of data sources took into account both the feasibility of obtaining the information in an automatic way as well as legal issues. We randomly selected 500 companies from VICO and for these, we sought the business description on Orbis, LexisNexis and Bloomberg databases. Among these data sources, we chose LexisNexis because it provides a better data coverage and allows us to include texts written by third parties, and not by the company itself, reducing risks of subjectivity and biases;
 - b. We identified a well-accepted definition of platform-based business, which has been used to guide the manual classification of business descriptions, composing the training set of the classification algorithm;
 - c. We built the training set, randomly extracting 5,000 companies from VICO. Of this initial list, we have been able to retrieve information from LexisNexis for about 20% of the companies. This sub-sample is representative of the entire sample according to firm's age, while is over representative of companies located in the UK compared to other countries;
 - d. We developed the classification algorithm, taking into account the training set specificity;
2. We performed the classification of more than 200 CVC investors of current VICO (MS26), according to the level of autonomy from their parent company and the strength of their financial versus strategic investment objectives. We used data retrieved from commercial

databases (e.g. Blommborg, LexisNexis) as well as public available information (e.g. websites of the CVC) and we included 3 additional variables characterizing the CVC:

- a. The level of autonomy of the CVC, which can be alternatively a business unit of the parent company, a CVC arm of the parent company, or a dedicated CVC fund;
- b. If the CVC has a dedicated website, separate from the parent company, established to perform the VC activity;
- c. The investment strategy of the CVC, classified from the CVC mission statement: the CVC may pursue strategic objectives, financial objectives or both.

2.3. Access and usages

The VICO database has been widely used in the European academic community, with 18 projects approved by M18 (the total number of applications was 29).

Given the fine-grained and wide scope of data on VC-backed firms, VICO can be used to produce large scale evidence on the ecology of the VC landscape in Europe. In particular, the main topics addressed by users include:

- ▶ VC investment patterns and selection process, e.g. how different types of VCs select their portfolio firms (Bertoni et al., 2019);
- ▶ The treatment effect of VCs on invested companies, e.g. the effect of VC value added activities on portfolio firms' performance in terms of growth (Guerini and Tenca, 2020) and valuation performance (Colombo & Montanaro, 2020);
- ▶ The internationalization and geography of VC activity in Europe, e.g. the emergence and/or agglomeration of VC markets around big metropolitan areas, the attraction of cross-border investments (Guerini and Hong, 2020; Guerini and Tenca, 2018; D'Adda et. al 2020);
- ▶ The complementarities between VCs and other sources of finance (i.e. BAs, crowdfunding...) thanks to VICO coverage of different types of investors in addition to VCs (Butticè et al., 2020; Capizzi et al., 2020);
- ▶ The link between innovation (e.g. radical inventions) and financing decisions of VCs (Colombo et al. 2020).

In what follows, we provide some highlights of the most advanced research works based on this topics.

Bertoni et al. (2019) analyze the changes in the patterns of investments for venture capital (VC) investors with different governance structures, i.e. independent, corporate, bank-affiliated and governmental VC investors. The authors compute specialization indexes for each investor type along five dimensions (industry and age of target company, geographical distance, syndicated investments, and cross border investments) and compare their evolution across four time periods (booming internet bubble: 1998–2001, bursting post-bubble: 2002–2004, post bubble recovery: 2005–2007, global financial crisis: 2008–2010, and post global financial crisis 2011–2014).

Figure 1. Specialization indexes for independent VC

Guerini and Tenca (2020) study whether and how different country-level institutional characteristics affect the performance of VC-backed firms. Matching VICO with a comparable sample of non-VC backed companies, the authors provide evidence on how more favorable institutional and entrepreneurial ecosystems stimulates the sales and employees growth of European start-ups (fig. 2).

Figure 2. Effect of VC on Sales and Employees growth in different EU countries

VC _{t-1}	SALES GROWTH				EMPLOYEES GROWTH			
	OLS	RE	FE	GMM	OLS	RE	FE	GMM
BEL	0.047 (0.062)	0.033 (0.080)	0.094 (0.136)	0.004 (0.150)	0.024 (0.025)	-0.021 (0.032)	0.014 (0.037)	0.023 (0.058)
FIN	0.054 (0.039)	0.034 (0.046)	0.206*** (0.065)	-0.005 (0.106)	-0.027 (0.021)	-0.053** (0.025)	-0.018 (0.034)	-0.030 (0.042)
FRA	0.117*** (0.016)	0.105*** (0.019)	0.086*** (0.025)	0.059 (0.038)	0.121*** (0.021)	0.121*** (0.021)	0.116*** (0.034)	0.207*** (0.064)
DEU	0.111*** (0.022)	0.104*** (0.030)	0.132*** (0.045)	0.081 (0.066)	0.042*** (0.015)	0.032* (0.018)	0.011 (0.035)	0.055 (0.036)
ITA	-0.183*** (0.060)	-0.212*** (0.073)	-0.113 (0.102)	-0.255 (0.222)	-0.017 (0.031)	-0.036 (0.037)	-0.018 (0.063)	-0.050 (0.082)
ESP	0.064** (0.032)	0.060 (0.038)	0.231*** (0.047)	-0.062 (0.079)	0.016 (0.018)	0.011 (0.022)	0.057** (0.028)	-0.088** (0.044)
UK	0.140*** (0.020)	0.115*** (0.028)	0.149*** (0.043)	0.267*** (0.061)	0.064*** (0.010)	0.043*** (0.014)	-0.038 (0.023)	0.032 (0.029)

Colombo & Montanaro (2020) use VICO to study how a sequence composed of multiple signals influences the valuation that startups receive at acquisition. Results show that a strong signal related to being VC-backed (e.g. being backed by a US investor) will make market observers set their expectations on the firm's quality at a higher level, so that becoming public on a less reputable market (e.g. in Europe rather than in the US) will decrease its valuation.

Butticè et al. (2020), using a unique dataset of 290 firms that successfully fundraised via the two most prominent UK equity crowdfunding portals and combining it with VICO, examine how different shareholder structures, i.e. the nominee vs. the direct shareholder structure, affect the attraction of subsequent VC financing. Results shows that: i) receiving equity crowdfunding facilitates the attraction of VC financing, ii) this association is stronger when the firm selected a nominee shareholder structure, iii) compared to BA-backed firms, equity crowdfunding through a nominee structure eases VC attraction.

Guerini and Hong (2020) examine whether there are positive externalities associated with international VC firms' penetration in the European VC market (fig. 3). The study focuses on how the presence of foreign VC firms in the local market affects performances of start-ups backed by domestic investors. Results suggest that domestic VC firms can obtain valuable know-how through forming syndicates with foreign VC firms, as prior experience with foreign VC firms is associated to greater performance of domestic VC investments.

Figure 3. Cross-border investments in Europe

Colombo et al. (2020) analyze 362 young European life science companies from VICO that received first-round investments from 281 VC investors between 2003 and 2015. The study analyses whether and how VC investors react to patents protecting radical inventions, which offer tremendous profit opportunities but have a high risk of failure (dark side). Results suggest that these companies are attractive investment targets for reputable VC investors but not for non reputable ones and that these reputable investors take action by syndicating their investments.

Finally, we plan to use the VICO dataset in methodological courses. In particular, the course “Panel Data Methods and Applications”, organized by Politecnico di Milano introduces the main features of panel data econometric models (e.g. fixed-effects vs. random-effects models), presenting use cases and examples based on the VICO dataset. The course originally scheduled in March, 2020, due to the covid-19 emergency, was postponed to November, 2020.

3. Outlook and next steps

As far as maintenance and deepening are concerned, we will continue according to the workplan until M24 (table 1 and table 2) when the first release of VICO is scheduled, performing the following activities: data cleaning, integration of accounting data and information on exits of new firms, classification of investor types, also for newly downloaded investors.

For the next year, we will proceed according to the workplan outlined in table 3 concerning maintenance activities (WP5) and table 4 concerning deepening activities (WP9). In particular, we will perform a second complete update of the VICO database (download of new venture capital deals and accounting data) for the period 2019-2020, starting from M27 and concluding with the second release of VICO in M42 (MS64 – WP5). This second release will include new data on innovative business models and classification of investor types (MS66 – WP9).

Table 3. Timetable Maintenance M24-M42

Time	Activity
M24	First release of updated VICO – MS32 (WP5).
M27	Download of venture capital deals and accounting data from source databases (Thomson Reuters Eikon, Zephyr, Crunchbase and Orbis) for the period 2019-2020 and from additional sources (e.g., Pitchbook) for the entire VICO time coverage 1998-2020.
M28	Download of information on exits (IPO/M&A) for new firms.
M29-M41	Integration, geocoding and data cleaning.
M42	Second release of updated VICO – MS64 (WP5).

Table 4. Timetable Deepening M24-M42

Time	Activity
M24	First release of updated VICO – MS32 (WP5).
M30	Data on innovative business model available for access – MS48 (WP9).
M34-M42	Classification of investor types (CVC, Business Angels and Crowdfunding).
M36-M42	Business model classification of newly added VICO companies.
M42	Second release of updated VICO (enlarged version, including data on innovative business models) – MS66 (WP9).

VICO is integrated with the other firm-level RISIS datasets through the FirmReg facility. FirmReg is a central facility within RISIS, which aims at uniquely identifying and tracking over time the businesses included in firms' datasets that are part of RISIS.

4. List of milestones and Deliverables (WP5, WP9)

List of Deliverables

Contribution to overall deliverables for WP5:

D5.1 – Consolidated work plan on Maintenance [M6]

D5.2 – First interim report on Maintenance [M18]

D5.3 – Second interim report on Maintenance [M36]

D5.4 – Final report on Maintenance [M46]

Contribution to overall deliverables for WP9:

D9.1 – Consolidated work plan on datasets development [M12]

D9.2 – Interim documentation on new datasets development [M30]

D9.3 – Full documentation on developments made on RISIS core datasets [M42]

D9.4 – Policy briefs on new developments and their policy relevance [M42]

List of milestones and status

Number (WP)	Title	Due Date	Description	Status
MS26 (WP9)	Investors data incorporated in VICO	18	VICO investors data available for access	Accomplished
MS32 (WP5)	Updated VICO 1	24	Updated database available for Access, reports on maintenance	Most tasks have been accomplished according to the workplan.
MS48 (WP9)	VICO and Cheetah enlarged versions with innovation patterns (version 1)	30	Data on innovation patterns (version 1) in VICO and Cheetah available for access	Pilot test concluded.
MS64 (WP5)	Updated VICO 2	42	Updated database available for Access, reports on maintenance	Activities will start in M24.
MS66 (WP9)	VICO and Cheetah enlarged versions with innovation patterns (version 2)	42	Data on innovation patterns (version 1) in VICO and Cheetah available for access	Activities will start in M30.

5. List of accesses

Applicant	Applicant institution	Project Title	Date
Suting Hong	ShanghaiTech University	Going Global to Stay Local: The Effect of International Syndication Experience on the Performance of Domestic Venture Capital Investments	25.06.2020
Diego D'Adda	Università Politecnica delle Marche	Cultural distance and Venture Capital investments	24.06.2020
Toby Chelton	Humboldt-Universität	Drivers of Venture Capital in Europe	05.06.2020
Barbara Antonioli Mantegazzini	Università della Svizzera Italiana	Innovative business models for energy and water companies	11.05.2020
Nico Zeiner	University of Mannheim	The treatment effect of VC on companies with inventions	17.04.2020
Saadat Saeed	Durham University Business School	Entrepreneurial Finance and New ventures	26.03.2020
Julia Mokhtar	School of Business and Economics, Maastricht	Value-creation in Young, Start-Up and Growth Ventures: Syndication of European-based Venture Capital Firms	11.03.2020
Francesca Di Pietro	Trinity College Dublin	Equity Crowdfunding Deal Structure and the Attraction of Venture Capital Investors	04.02.2020
Denisa Naidin	Université Toulouse 1 Capitole	Innovation management in the space sector	10.01.2020
Jana Reuther	Universität St.Gallen	Corporate Venutre Capital - the "Blitzkrieg" of the 21th century, running over corporate strategy	07.01.2020
Ine Paeleman	University of Antwerp	How will VC investors influence the level and type of slack resources?	27.12.2019
Niels Kuschmierz	TU Dortmund University	PhD research on CVC activities (follow-on investments, knowledge spillovers, and European CVC market dynamisms)	11.07.2019
Juan Carlos Salazar Elena	Universidad Autonoma de Madrid	Policy for High-Growth innovative enterprises	05.07.2019
Nico Lehnertz	Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf	Patterns of bank-affiliated venture capital in Europe - A market overview	03.07.2019
Alina Fesenko	Universitat de Barcelona	Deal Syndication of VC Investments from the venture-backed companies' perspective	10.05.2019
Julian Giessing	Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg	The soft budget constraint of VCs - Do startups use investor money efficiently?	23.03.2019
Anna Theresa Bühle	ZEW - Zentrum für Europäische Wirtschaftsforschung	The effect of tax loss provisions on the venture capital financing of start-ups	20.03.2019
Nico Zeiner	University of Mannheim	The perception of radical invention by Venture Capitalists	11.03.2019

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